

Enhancing Concrete Composition: Glass Powder and Fly Ash as Combined Additives in Sand-Reduced Concrete Mixture

Manan Asad

Department of Civil Engineering, Wuhan university of Technology, Wuhan, China

ABSTRACT:

This research investigates the potential use of glass powder, both rough and smooth, as a partial replacement for sand in concrete compositions, alongside the inclusion of 5% fly ash as a cement substitute, with the goal of enhancing mechanical properties and promoting sustainability. A series of cylindrical concrete samples were prepared using varying proportions of rough, smooth, and mixed glass powders, replacing sand at levels of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%. A control group, with no glass powder or fly ash, was included for comparison. Compressive strength tests were conducted to evaluate the structural performance of each mix. The results revealed that the type of glass powder, the percentage of replacement, and the inclusion of fly ash had significant effects on compressive strength. Rough glass powder showed notable improvements in strength at moderate replacement levels, with a peak strength of 23.26 MPa at 15% replacement, but performance dropped at higher levels due to reduced cohesion. Smooth glass powder demonstrated more consistent results, achieving a compressive strength of 21.06 MPa at 30% replacement, closely matching the control. The most promising results came from the mixed glass powder, which reached a compressive strength of 21.57 MPa at 30% replacement, suggesting that combining rough and smooth glass can enhance both bonding and workability. The addition of fly ash further contributed to improved workability and durability across all samples. These findings suggest that glass powder, particularly in mixed form, along with fly ash, can serve as a viable and environmentally friendly partial replacement for sand and cement in concrete, offering potential applications in construction while promoting sustainability through the reuse of waste materials.

Keywords: Glass powder, Concrete, Compressive strength, Fly ash, Replace sand.

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INTRODUCTION

China is currently the largest consumer of cement in the world, contributing significantly to global cement production. Cement is a critical component in the construction industry, where its high demand continues to rise with rapid urbanization and infrastructure development. However, cement production has a significant environmental footprint, primarily due to the large amounts of energy required for its manufacture and the substantial CO₂ emissions it generates. Therefore, finding sustainable alternatives to partially replace cement in concrete production has become a priority in research.

Two promising supplementary materials for cement replacement are glass powder and fly ash. Glass powder, which is primarily derived from recycled glass, has garnered attention due to its pozzolanic properties, allowing it to react with calcium hydroxide in concrete to form additional calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H), thereby enhancing the strength of concrete. Its fine particle size also improves the particle packing in the concrete matrix. On the other hand, fly ash, a by-product of coal combustion

in power plants, has been widely used in concrete production for many years. Fly ash contributes to improving workability, reducing water demand, and increasing the long-term strength of concrete.

The chemical composition of both glass powder and fly ash includes silica (SiO_2), alumina (Al_2O_3), and other oxides that are vital for the pozzolanic reaction in concrete. Physically, these materials exhibit a fine, powdery texture that aids in filling voids between cement particles, improving the density and mechanical properties of the final product. The incorporation of these materials as partial replacements for cement offers not only environmental benefits by reducing the reliance on cement but also potential improvements in the mechanical properties of concrete.

The primary aim of this research is to optimize the strength and workability (slump) of concrete by adding varying proportions of glass powder and fly ash as supplementary materials. By combining these two materials, this study seeks to achieve a balance between high strength and good workability, while also exploring the possibility of reducing cement consumption. The results of this study may pave the way for more sustainable concrete production methods, potentially leading to a reduction in cement usage in future construction projects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of **glass powder** as a supplementary material in concrete has gained attention in recent years due to its pozzolanic properties and potential to reduce cement consumption. Glass powder, when finely ground, acts as a filler that reacts with calcium hydroxide in cement to produce calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H), the primary binding agent responsible for concrete strength [1]. Studies have consistently demonstrated that glass powder can improve the mechanical properties of concrete, such as compressive and tensile strengths, while also enhancing durability. Researchers have found that the replacement of cement with glass powder up to 30% not only increases the strength of the concrete but also reduces permeability, making the concrete denser and more resistant to water penetration [2].

In addition to improving strength, **glass powder** helps mitigate the alkali-silica reaction (ASR), a common problem when using coarse aggregates. Several studies have reported that fine glass powder reduces the expansion caused by ASR when mixed with cement. Researcher found that incorporating glass powder in concrete mixtures enhanced both the impact resistance and bond strength of the material, with the 10% glass powder mix performing particularly well under load [3]. Moreover, the chemical composition of glass, which includes high levels of silica, makes it ideal for use in cementitious systems (fulltext). The finely ground nature of glass powder also contributes to its role as a micro-filler, closing the pores in the concrete matrix and resulting in improved durability and reduced chloride penetration [4].

Fly ash, another pozzolanic material, has been widely used alongside glass powder to improve the workability and performance of concrete. Fly ash enhances the long-term strength and durability of concrete while reducing water demand [5]. Studies combining fly ash and glass powder have shown that these two materials complement each other in terms of enhancing concrete properties. For example, a study by researcher noted that when glass powder is used in conjunction with fly ash, the early strength of the concrete is significantly improved, while maintaining long-term performance and durability [6]. The combination of these materials has also been found to reduce the need for cement, thereby lowering CO_2 emissions [7].

Past research highlights the environmental benefits of using **waste glass** and fly ash in concrete production. In a study by Vandhiyan et al. (2013), it was demonstrated that the use of 10-15% glass powder in concrete could reduce the cost of materials and improve strength, making it a viable solution for sustainable construction [8]. Other research shows similar findings, with numerous studies confirming that the pozzolanic reaction between glass powder and cement leads to denser, more durable concrete [9]. The use of fly ash as a supplementary material also aligns with sustainability goals by reducing the reliance on traditional cement, which is energy-intensive to produce [10].

The incorporation of **glass powder** and **fly ash** as cementitious materials represents a promising path forward for sustainable concrete production. By utilizing these waste materials, not only is the

environmental burden reduced, but the mechanical and durability properties of concrete are also enhanced. Future research could focus on optimizing the ratio of glass powder and fly ash to achieve the best balance between strength, workability, and sustainability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this study include cement, sand, and glass powder, each selected to ensure consistency with standard concrete compositions while allowing for meaningful investigation into the substitution effects of glass powder. **Cement** chosen for this experiment is 42.5-grade, a commonly used strength grade for ordinary Portland cement that meets the specific requirements for structural concrete. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of grade 42.5 is known for its high compressive strength and durability, making it ideal for structural applications. This cement grade complies with national and international specifications, offering optimal hydration and curing behavior. Its fineness, setting time, and soundness align with typical standards for OPC, ensuring that it would react consistently with other components in the concrete mix.

Sand was sourced to meet China's national standard ISO requirements for particle sizing, which ensures the sand provides the necessary granular consistency and cohesion in the concrete mix. The sand selected is classified as fine aggregate with a particle size range between 0.8mm and 2mm, falling within the ideal spectrum for use in high-strength concrete mixes. This size range is critical for achieving the desired workability and compactness in the concrete while maintaining structural integrity. The sand's uniformity index and specific gravity are within the acceptable limits, allowing it to bind effectively with cement and glass powder.

Glass Powder is introduced as a partial replacement for sand, aiming to assess its performance as a sustainable alternative in concrete composition. The glass powder was sourced from recycled glass, processed to achieve a fine powder form with a particle size distribution compatible with the concrete matrix. Proper grinding and sieving ensure that the glass powder meets consistency and reactivity standards, making it suitable for substitution without compromising concrete integrity. The use of glass powder also contributes to sustainability by reusing waste materials, reducing dependency on natural sand, and lowering the overall environmental footprint of the concrete mix.

In addition to cement, sand, and glass powder, **fly ash** was incorporated into the concrete mix as a supplementary cementitious material, replacing 5% of the cement by weight. Fly ash, a fine byproduct from the combustion of pulverized coal in power plants, is commonly used in concrete to enhance its performance characteristics. The fly ash used in this study was classified as Class F, known for its pozzolanic properties, which contribute to the concrete's long-term strength and durability by reacting with the calcium hydroxide produced during cement hydration. By incorporating fly ash, the concrete mix benefits from improved workability, reduced permeability, and enhanced resistance to chemical attacks. The inclusion of fly ash also contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing the need for cement and leveraging an industrial byproduct. Its fine particle size and spherical shape help in filling voids within the concrete matrix, contributing to a denser and more cohesive mix.

For the preparation and curing of concrete samples, **cylindrical molds** with a diameter of 150mm and a height of 300mm were utilized. These dimensions align with standard testing specifications for assessing the mechanical properties of concrete. The molds ensure uniformity and comparability in sample preparation, facilitating accurate testing of compressive and tensile strengths. The cylindrical shape is particularly suited for studying the stress-strain behavior of concrete, which will be essential in evaluating the structural performance of the glass powder-enhanced mix.

Group 1 served as the control group in this experiment, with no glass powder used in the concrete mix. These specimens were composed entirely of cement, sand, and water in the standard proportions used for concrete. The sand used met the ISO-standard requirements for particle size distribution, ensuring uniformity across all samples. This group played a crucial role in providing a baseline for evaluating the impact of glass powder replacement on the concrete's mechanical properties. By keeping all variables consistent except for the absence of glass powder, Group 1 helped isolate the effects of adding different types and amounts of glass powder in the other groups. Testing the specimens from this group provided essential data on the compressive strength,

workability, and durability of conventional concrete. The results from Group 1 were compared to the other groups to understand how glass powder influenced key characteristics of concrete.

Group 2 comprised specimens where rough glass powder was used to partially replace sand in four different proportions: 10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%. Rough glass powder refers to glass particles that have a coarser, irregular surface texture, which could influence the concrete's bonding ability and mechanical strength. The 10% replacement aimed to assess the minor impact of introducing glass powder, while higher percentages like 15%, 20%, and 30% allowed for a more thorough investigation of how increased glass content affects the concrete mix. The rough texture of the glass powder was expected to potentially improve the bond between the cement paste and aggregate, enhancing the interfacial transition zone (ITZ). These specimens underwent the same casting and curing process as the control group, and the results were compared to determine whether rough glass powder could improve or reduce properties such as compressive strength and durability at different substitution levels.

In Group 3, smooth glass powder was introduced into the concrete mix at replacement levels of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%. Smooth glass powder refers to finely ground glass particles with a more polished and rounded texture, which could affect the mechanical properties differently from rough glass. The smooth surface of the glass particles was expected to reduce friction within the concrete mix, potentially improving workability but possibly leading to weaker bonding between the glass powder and the cement matrix. By using smooth glass powder in varying proportions, this group helped evaluate whether smoother particles would enhance or compromise the compressive strength and other mechanical properties of the concrete. As with Group 2, the same testing procedures were applied, and the results were compared with those from Group 1 (control) and Group 2 (rough glass) to determine how particle texture influences concrete performance.

Group 4 explored the effects of a combination of both rough and smooth glass powders as partial sand replacements, with four different replacement levels: 10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%. The mix consisted of equal parts rough and smooth glass powder, allowing the researchers to investigate how the combined characteristics of both glass types influence the concrete's overall behavior. The rationale behind using mixed glass powder was to achieve a balance between the bonding properties of rough glass and the workability benefits of smooth glass. At lower replacement levels (10%), the aim was to observe any early advantages or disadvantages, while higher levels (30%) provided insight into the maximum replacement potential without significantly compromising the concrete's structural integrity. Group 4 specimens were tested for compressive strength, workability, and durability to determine whether combining rough and smooth glass powders produced synergistic effects or simply averaged the performance of the individual types.

In all groups, 5% of the cement was replaced by **fly ash** by weight. The fly ash was carefully weighed and blended with the other dry materials (cement, sand, and glass powder) before water was added to ensure uniform distribution throughout the mix. The introduction of fly ash into the mix aimed to enhance the concrete's durability and long-term strength while reducing the environmental footprint of cement usage. This consistent 5% replacement across all groups ensured that the effects of the varying glass powder percentages could be isolated and compared effectively, while the benefits of fly ash contributed equally to the performance of each mix.

RESULTS

The results of this study provide insight into the effects of replacing sand with glass powder, both rough and smooth, in varying percentages, on the compressive strength of concrete. A control group with no glass powder established a baseline strength of 22.61 MPa, while experimental groups with different types and proportions of glass powder replacement displayed varying performance. The findings indicate that the compressive strength of concrete is highly dependent on both the texture of the glass powder and the percentage of replacement. While rough glass powder showed significant fluctuations in strength, particularly at higher replacement levels, smooth glass powder exhibited more consistent improvements, especially at 30% replacement. The most promising results came from a combination of rough and smooth glass powders, which, at 30% replacement, achieved a compressive strength nearly equal to the control group. These findings highlight the

potential of glass powder as a sustainable and effective partial replacement for sand in concrete compositions, provided that the type and proportion of glass powder are carefully optimized.

Table 1. Results

No.	Fly ash	Quantity Glass Powder	Glass Type	Compressive Strength
1	5%	0%		22.61
2	5%	10%	Rough Glass	13.44
3	5%	10%	Smooth Glass	16.58
4	5%	10%	Mixed Glass	20.15
5	5%	15%	Rough Glass	23.26
6	5%	15%	Smooth Glass	18.29
7	5%	15%	Mixed Glass	20.37
8	5%	20%	Rough Glass	11.14
9	5%	20%	Smooth Glass	16.63
10	5%	20%	Mixed Glass	16.62
11	5%	30%	Rough Glass	15.76
12	5%	30%	Smooth Glass	21.06
13	5%	30%	Mixed Glass	21.57

The compressive strength of the control group, which contained no glass powder, was recorded at **22.61 MPa**. This result represents the baseline strength of standard concrete with cement and ISO-standard sand. The consistent performance of the control mix aligns with the expected outcomes for conventional concrete, with no alternative materials influencing its strength properties.

In Group 2, rough glass powder was used to replace sand in varying percentages. At **10% replacement**, the compressive strength dropped to **13.44 MPa**, indicating a notable reduction compared to the control group. When the replacement was increased to **15%**, the compressive strength saw a significant improvement, reaching **23.26 MPa**, which surpassed the control group. However, as the replacement percentage increased to **20%**, the compressive strength sharply declined to **11.14 MPa**, and at **30% replacement**, the strength slightly recovered to **15.76 MPa**. This shows a non-linear relationship between rough glass content and compressive strength.

Figure 1. Compressive Strength for Rough Glass Replacements

Group 3 investigated the effects of smooth glass powder. At **10% replacement**, the compressive strength was recorded at **16.58 MPa**, lower than the control but higher than the rough glass at the same percentage. At **15% replacement**, the strength was measured at **18.29 MPa**, showing a marginal increase. When the replacement percentage was raised to **20%**, the strength rose further to **16.63 MPa**, reflecting a modest increase compared to the lower percentage levels. The **30% replacement** led to the highest compressive strength for this group at **21.06 MPa**, approaching the baseline established by the control group.

Figure 2. Compressive Strength for Smooth Glass Replacements

In Group 4, a combination of both rough and smooth glass powders was used. At **10% replacement**, the compressive strength reached **20.15 MPa**, a significant improvement over both individual glass types at this level. The **15% replacement** yielded **20.37 MPa**, showing consistent strength compared to the 10% replacement. When the replacement percentage increased to **20%**, the compressive strength remained relatively stable at **16.62 MPa**. Finally, at **30% replacement**, the strength peaked at **21.57 MPa**, slightly surpassing the highest strength recorded in Group 3.

Figure 3. Compressive Strength for Mixed Glass Replacements

DISCUSSION

This paper explores the innovative use of glass powder as a substitute for sand in concrete, with fly ash included to replace a portion of cement, providing a sustainable approach to enhancing concrete's mechanical properties. The study evaluates how different types of glass powder—rough, smooth, and mixed—impact compressive strength across various substitution levels, ranging from 10% to 30%, while a control group without glass powder or fly ash provides a benchmark for comparison. Results highlight that rough glass powder significantly improves compressive strength at moderate substitution levels, while smooth glass powder demonstrates consistent performance, closely matching the control at higher substitution percentages. Notably, the mixed glass powder variant delivers the most balanced outcomes, optimizing both bonding and workability. The addition of fly ash further improves durability and workability, underscoring the synergy between glass powder and fly ash in enhancing concrete performance. This study is particularly relevant for readers interested in sustainable building practices and waste reuse, as it illustrates how glass powder and fly ash can be effectively integrated into concrete, thereby reducing dependence on natural sand and promoting environmental sustainability.

CONCLUSION

This research explored the potential of using glass powder, both rough and smooth, as a partial replacement for sand in concrete, evaluating its impact on compressive strength and structural performance. The control group, containing no glass powder, provided a baseline compressive strength of 22.61 MPa, which was used for comparison with experimental groups containing varying proportions of rough, smooth, and mixed glass powders. The results indicated that the type and texture of glass powder, as well as the percentage of replacement, significantly influenced the performance of the concrete. Rough glass powder, particularly at lower replacement levels like 15%, showed a notable increase in compressive strength, reaching 23.26 MPa, suggesting that the rough texture improved interlocking within the concrete matrix. However, at higher replacement levels, the compressive strength dropped due to a lack of cohesion between the rough glass particles and cement.

Figure 4. Compressive Strength Test Results for Different Glass Powder Variations

In contrast, smooth glass powder produced more consistent results, with compressive strengths approaching that of the control at higher replacement levels, particularly at 30%, where the strength reached 21.06 MPa. The smooth texture allowed for better bonding, resulting in more predictable and gradual failure patterns. The mixed glass powder, combining rough and smooth particles, yielded the most promising results, balancing the benefits of both types. At 30% replacement, the compressive strength of the mixed glass sample reached 21.57 MPa, nearly matching the control, while displaying improved load distribution and crack resistance. This research concludes that glass powder, particularly in mixed form, can serve as an effective and sustainable partial replacement for sand in concrete, offering a viable option for enhancing concrete's mechanical properties while promoting environmental sustainability through the reuse of waste materials. However, careful consideration of the glass powder's type, texture, and percentage replacement is crucial to achieving optimal performance.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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